

Synthesis and characterization of gold nanoparticles using *Mimosops elengi* aqueous extract

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Manuscript received online 12 April 2012, revised 22 June 2012, accepted 25 June 2012

Abstract : This work reports the green synthesis of gold nanoparticles (Au NPs) by reduction of AuCl₄ using extract of *Mimosops elengi* (*M. elengi*) pericarp. *M. elengi* is widely used in ayurvedic medicines and also in antiurolithiatic and antioxidant activities. Stable Au NPs were formed within 5 min at room temperature. Synthesized Au NPs were characterized using different techniques such as UV-Vis spectrophotometer, Transmission electron microscopy (TEM), Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and X-ray diffraction (XRD). Formation of Au NPs was confirmed by the absorption band at 537 nm. XRD showed that the synthesized Au NPs were crystalline. TEM revealed that the particle size was in the range of 2–20 nm. The synthesized Au NPs were stable for 3 months. This enhanced stabilization was due to the binding of biomolecules onto the surface of metal nanoparticles which was evidenced by FT-IR measurements. This biological method facilitated much faster synthesis of Au NPs as an alternative to other chemical methods in a greener way.

Keywords : *M. elengi*, gold nanoparticles, green synthesis, biomolecules.

Introduction

The noble metals such as gold (Au), silver (Ag) and platinum (Pt) play very important roles in research by virtue of their incredible and flexible physical, chemical, biological and opto-electrical properties. These noble metal nanoparticles are widely used in the products that directly come in contact with the human body, such as shampoos, soaps, detergents, cosmetic products and tooth-pastes¹. Noble metal nanoparticles such as gold have been widely using in medical applications such as drug delivery and tumor imaging². Well established chemical methods are available to synthesize Au NPs. But in most of the chemical methods, the used reducing agents and stabilizers were toxic in nature^{3–6}. And there are several other methods such as thermal decomposition⁷, vapor deposition⁸ etc. used for synthesis of Au NPs which are expensive and time-consuming. In recent years the green synthesis of Au NPs using plants extracts has engrossed the attention of many researchers because of their simplicity and harmless by-products. Synthesis of Au NPs using various plant extracts such as *Terminalia chebula*²,

Palm oil⁴, Cypress leaves⁹, *Trigonella foenum-greecum*¹⁰, Curciferous vegetables¹¹ and *Macrotyloma uniflorum*¹² have been reported. This diversified field is still gaining attention because of its potential to make NPs of varying sizes and properties. The selected plant species (*M. elengi*) for synthesizing Au NPs is widely used in traditional medicines for treating inflammation and bleeding of gums, chronic dysentery and snakes bite^{13,14}. The extracts of various parts are known for their antiurolithiatic and antioxidant activity¹⁵. The polyphenols and tannins present in the extract are responsible for the formation of Au NPs. This paper describes the potential of *M. elengi* aqueous extract in the synthesis of Au NPs. Multi functionality i.e. both as reducing and capping ability of *M. elengi* aqueous extract was described. Synthesized NPs have been monitored and characterized using UV-Vis, TEM, FTIR and XRD.

Results and discussion

UV-Vis spectroscopy is one of the important techniques to validate the stability of NPs in aqueous me-

dium. The formation of Au NPs was monitored by visual color change and UV-Visible spectroscopy (Fig. 1). The visual color change from yellow to pink is because of surface plasmon resonance (SPR) which arises due to free

Fig. 1. UV-Visible spectra of Au NPs.

movement of electrons induced by interacting magnetic field¹⁶. The spectrum was recorded in the range of 400–900 nm. The sharp band was observed at 537 nm which indicates the presence of spherical Au NPs. It is known that spherical NPs exhibit single peak^{17,18}. The present work supports similar report^{17,18}. Besides spherical Au NPs other shapes such as triangular NPs (540 nm to near IR region¹⁹), nano rods (643 to 674 nm²⁰), hexagonal NPs (900 to 1100 nm²⁰).

Typical TEM images of the synthesized Au NPs are shown in the Fig. 2a. The results obtained from TEM analysis gives clear information about size and shape of the synthesized Au NPs. The Au NPs were found to be

well dispersed, almost isotropic and spherically shaped. This is in clear agreement with the UV-Vis spectra of Au NPs (Fig. 1). The size of Au NPs is in the range of 2–20 nm. But a few triangle and pentagonal shaped Au NPs can be seen in TEM images which are due to inadequacy of available biomolecules to control the size. This little anisotropy is due to rapid reduction process, room temperature sintering and self assembly of the weakly protected spherical NPs. d-spacing was measured to be 2.34 Å (Fig. 2b), which is in close conformity with the spacing between the (1 1 1) plane of FCC gold (2.35 Å) (JCPDS No. 00-04-0784).

The XRD pattern of Au NPs synthesized by *M. elengi* extract is shown in Fig. 3. The peaks in X-ray diffraction pattern appear at 38.16, 44.35 and 64.66 which could be consigned to be (1 1 1), (2 0 0) and (2 2 0) of cubic Au NPs respectively and were in conformity with database of JCPDS (Joint Committee for Powder diffraction studies) Card No. 00-004-0784. Crystalline nature of the synthesized Au NPs was confirmed from the XRD pattern.

Capping of bio molecules was confirmed by FTIR studies of *M. elengi* and purified Au NPs. FTIR reports of *M. elengi* (Fig. 4a) showed bands at 3400 cm⁻¹ corresponds to -OH stretching, 2929 and 1614 cm⁻¹ represents aliphatic -C-H stretching and -C=O stretching. FTIR spectrum of purified Au NPs displayed IR bands at 3496, 2922, 2857, 1649, 1539, 1419, 1338 and 1039 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 4b). The bands at 3496 and at around 2900 cm⁻¹ correspond to -OH stretching and aliphatic -C-H stretching. The peaks at 1649 and 1539 cm⁻¹ are due to -C=O stretching and -C=C stretching. The bands 1419, 1338 and 1039 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to -C-N, -C-O and -C-O-C stretching modes respectively. This observation clears biomolecular capping onto the surface of Au NPs which

Fig. 2. (a) TEM images of Au NPs, (b) single nano crystal showing d-spacing and (c) histogram showing particle size distribution.

Fig. 3. XRD pattern of synthesized Au NPs.

keeps them stable for extended periods and promising for further applications.

Experimental

Materials :

Chloroauric acid (HAuCl_4) was purchased from SD fine chemicals, India. *Mimosops elengi* seeds were collected from VIT University campus located at Vellore. Milli-Q water was used throughout the experiment.

Preparation of *M. elengi* extract :

The pericarp was separated from the collected *M. elengi* fruits which was air-dried for one week with precaution to avoid external contamination and stored. Prior to the experiment, the stored pericarp was dried in an oven for 2 h at 100 °C and 1.0 g of this powder was mixed with 100 mL of Milli-Q water and heated at 90 °C on a temperature controlled water bath for 1 h, cooled and filtered using 0.2 μm cellulose nitrate membrane filter papers.

Fig. 4. FTIR spectra of (a) *M. elengi* powder and (b) purified Au NPs.

Synthesis of gold nanoparticles :

10 mL of *M. elengi* aqueous extract was added to 2 mL of 1 mM HAuCl₄ solution and mixed thoroughly. Formation of Au NPs was noticed at room temperature through a visual color change from yellow to ruby red within 5 min of the addition of the extract.

Characterization :

UV-Visible spectroscopy :

Initially, the synthesized Au NPs were characterized using UV-Visible spectroscopy. The reduction was monitored from 400 to 900 nm on Jasco V-670 spectrophotometer after diluting the sample 20 times with Milli-Q water. The spectrum was recorded using Milli-Q water as blank. The recorded data was then plotted using Origin 6.1 software.

X-Ray diffraction :

The synthesized Au NPs were washed and purified using ethanol after 2 rounds of centrifugation at 15000 rpm and then X-ray diffraction analysis was carried out (Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer with Cu K α radiation, $\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$). The scanning was done between 20° to 90° at 0.02°/0.3 s with time constant of 2 s. The nickel monochromatic filters the wave at tube voltage of 40 kV with tube current of 30 mA. Before the analysis, the instrument was calibrated using Lanthanum hexaboride (LaB₆).

Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy :

Purified Au NPs were dried in an oven and the powder form was subjected to FT-IR spectral measurements. The analysis was carried out using *M. elengi* pericarp powder as control on a Shimadzu Fourier transformation infrared spectrophotometer IR Affinity-1 instrument, using KBr pellet in the diffuse reflectance mode at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

Transmission electron microscopy :

The morphology and size of Au NPs synthesized were characterized by Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) (JEOL JEM 2100 High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscope). 1 mL of the reaction mixture was diluted 5-fold using Milli-Q water followed by sonication using ultrasonic bath and the reaction mixture was dropped on Cu grid and dried in vacuum. TEM micrograms were taken at the acceleration voltage of 200 kV.

Conclusion :

The synthesis of Au NPs by *M. elengi* extract as a reducing agent was rapid and completed within 5 min.

Analysis showed the average crystalline particle size of 9.5 nm with spherical shape. Polyphenols and tannins present in the extract were responsible for the formation and stabilization of Au NPs. Since *M. elengi* has many medicinal applications, the synthesized NPs could be used further for various medical and technological applications.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to VIT University, Vellore for the help and platform given to do this work. We are highly thankful to SAS, VIT University for providing the basic characterization facilities.

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